

SHORT NOTES

FORMATION OF SILVER¹⁰⁹ BY BOMBARDMENT OF ENRICHED CADMIUM¹⁰⁶ WITH PROTONS*

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Neutron-deficient Ag¹⁰⁹ was previously prepared (Haldar and Wiig, *Phys. Rev.*, 1954, **94**, 1713) by spallation of silver with 80, 100 and 170 Mev protons and identified by milking the Pd¹⁰⁹ daughter. At lower proton energies a (p, α) reaction on Cd¹⁰⁶ would be expected to produce Ag¹⁰⁹. Since the abundance of Cd¹⁰⁶ in natural cadmium is only 1.22%, greatly enhanced activity due to Ag¹⁰⁹ is to be expected on bombarding an enriched Cd¹⁰⁶ sample.

Enriched Cd¹⁰⁶ (32.9%)** as CdO and as CdNH₄PO₄·H₂O was bombarded for one hour with protons of 60 and 40 Mev energy in the internal beam of the 130-inch cyclotron of the University of Rochester. Natural cadmium in the form of metal was also bombarded at 60 Mev. The bombarded targets were dissolved in nitric acid, silver carrier was added and silver activity was separated as silver chloride. The latter, after purification by the procedures, used earlier (*loc. cit.*), was counted in a β-proportional counter, a scintillation counter and an X-ray proportional counter.

The silver activity obtained from enriched Cd¹⁰⁶ targets and measured with the first two counters was found to decay with half lives of 27 minutes and 1.07 hours along with a half life of about 5 hours, the activity of which was less than 1% of the total activity. With the X-ray counter, silver activities of 18 minutes and 1.1 hours were obtained from the CdO target. The silver activity separated from the metallic cadmium target decayed with half lives of 20 minutes, 1.1 hours, 2.6 hours and 5.2 hours, as measured with the β-proportional counter. All the 1.1-hour activities showed the same radiation characteristics as those exhibited by the 1.1 hour Ag¹⁰⁹ produced earlier (*loc. cit.*). The 27-minute activity is due to Ag¹⁰⁹/ or Ag¹⁰⁴. The 18 minute activity is probably associated with Ag¹⁰² which, according to the most recent "Table of Isotopes" (Hollander, Perlman and Seaborg, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1953, **25**, 469), has a half life of 16 minutes.

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The ratio of the Ag^{103} activities obtained at 60 Mev from enriched and normal cadmium, calculated to the end of bombardment and corrected for the difference in target material, was found to be 20 to 1 as compared with an enrichment factor of 27. The cyclotron beam was not monitored but the intensity was approximately the same. Thus, the 1.1 hour-activity is produced from Cd^{106} and a (p, α) reaction to produce Ag^{103} is suggested.

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QUANTITATIVE ISOLATION OF DL-GLUTAMIC ACID FROM A MIXTURE OF DL-2-PYRROLIDONE-5-CARBOXYLIC ACID AND DL-GLUTAMYLGLUTAMIC ACID

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When glutamic acid is isolated from a protein by acid hydrolysis, it is generally assumed that glutamic acid is present in the protein as a straight-chain peptide. During this investigation it is shown that a quantitative yield of DL-glutamic acid is obtained when a mixture of DL-2-pyrrolidone-5-carboxylic acid and the dipeptide DL-glutamylglutamic acid is hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid. This suggests that in a natural protein glutamic acid may be present as a linear peptide as well as a peptide of 2-pyrrolidone-6-carboxylic acid (the cyclic analogue).

A mixture of 129 mg. of DL-2-pyrrolidone-5-carboxylic acid and 276 mg. of DL-glutamylglutamic acid and 25 c.c. of 6N-HCl was refluxed on a water-bath for 16 hours. It was then evaporated in vacuum when 541 mg. of a yellowish white crystalline material was obtained. Twice crystallisation of this from distilled water under reduced pressure in a desiccator gave 538 mg. of colorless prismatic crystals, m.p. 196°. (Found: N, 7.56. Calc: N, 7.63%). Its mixed m.p. with a genuine sample of DL-glutamic acid hydrochloride was also 196°. Its R_f value was also identical with that of genuine glutamic acid hydrochloride.

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